

A greener approach for the one-pot synthesis of substituted thiazolidinones by using an efficient and recyclable ionic liquid

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Abstract : A convenient protocol for the synthesis of 2,3-diarylthiazolidin-4-one have been achieved by one-pot condensation of aryl or heteroaryl amine, aryl aldehyde and 2-mercaptopropionic acid in 3-butyl-1-methyl-1H-imidazol-3-iumtrifluoroacetate as ionic liquid [BMIM][TFA] is described. Reported ionic liquid easy to make, recycle and reuse up to three times in good to excellent yields. Synthesized compounds were fully characterized by their spectroscopic data.

Keywords : Heterocycles, thiazolidone, ionic liquid, green chemistry, one-pot synthesis.

Introduction

Nitrogen containing heterocycles are structural component of a variety of biologically active natural and non-natural compounds¹. In the same, nitrogen and sulphur containing heterocycles have been under investigation for a long time because of their important medicinal properties². Among these type of molecules, thiazolidinone represents a class of chemical entity with interesting pharmacological and a biological activity includes anti-inflammatory³, analgesic properties⁴, antituberculosic⁵, anti-HIV⁶, cardio protective⁷, anti-cancer⁸, anticonvulsant⁹, antiviral¹⁰, antifungal¹¹, antimicrobial¹². They act as antioxidant and play an important role in the immune system¹³. Therefore, the synthesis of thiazolidone derivatives is currently of much importance. There are numerous approaches reported in the literature for the construction of thiazolidones¹⁴. However, in above some reported protocols grieve from one or more drawbacks like prolonged reaction times, use of ecologically uncomplimentary solvents and often low yields. Therefore, the development of mild, efficient and versatile method is still strongly required.

Most of the synthetic procedures are associated with

typical reaction conditions, poor yields and hazard solvents. In view of the diversified applications described above, we hereby report the first effective one-pot three component synthesis of thiazolidinones derivatives. The syntheses were performed in ecologically friendly conditions with the use of acidic ionic liquids¹⁵ and afforded the desired products in high yield. Ionic liquids have found numerous applications not only as environmentally benign reaction media, but also as catalysts and reagents¹⁶. From this perspective, combining synthetic potentialities of multi chemical reactions with the dual properties of ionic liquids as solvents and catalyst results in the development of valuable eco-compatible organic synthesis procedures¹⁷.

Materials and method :

Synthesis of ionic liquid :

Synthesis of 3-butyl-1-methyl-1H-imidazol-3-ium-bromide [BMIM][Br] :

To the stirring solution of compound **1a** (50 g, 0.609 mole) was added dropwise compound **1b** (83.33 g, 0.6699 mole). Reaction mixture was stirred at 80 °C for 12 h. Completion of reaction on TLC, light yellow viscous reaction mass was obtained as desired

[BMIM][Br]. Into this reaction mixture toluene was added and stirred again for 30 min. Layer was separated and lower layer was distilled under high vacuum at 90–100 °C. Desired product was isolated as crude.

Crude was crystallized by ethyl acetate and then evaporate a white solid obtained with 92% yield.

Synthesis of 3-butyl-1-methyl-1H-imidazol-3-iumtrifluoroacetate [BMIM][TFA] :

Anion-exchange : To the stirring solution of compound [BMIM][Br] (15 g, 0.059 mole) add water 22 g then added lotwise sodium trifluoroacetate (8.57 g, 0.6699 mole). Reaction mixture was stirred for 12 h. Reaction mass distilled out at 70–75 °C under reduces pressure at 550 mm Hg. Add dichloromethane 20 g into the crude mass. Stirring for 1 h than filter by Whatman filter paper. Filtrated complete distilled out at 60–65 °C without vacuum. Light yellow liquids obtained pH acidic. Yield 95% obtained.

Synthesis of 2,3-diarylthiazolidin-4-one (4a-g) :

Charge 6-methylpyridin-2-amine (**1**) (1 mole/equiv) and 4-fluorobenzaldehyde (**3a-g**) (1.1 mole/equiv) and acidic ionic liquids [BMIM][TFA] (2 mole/equiv) into round bottom flask under magnetic stirring, heating start up to 70±2 °C, stirring for 1 h, charge 2-mercaptopropionic acid (**2**) and stirring for 8 to 10 h at 70±2 °C. The progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC. After completion of reaction, the reac-

tion mixture was cool up to 40±2 °C, add water (10 mole/equiv) and stirring for 30 min, filter the reaction mass by Whatman filter paper under vacuum, white solid obtained with 92–94% yield, solid crystallized by methanol. Filterate complete distilled out at 80–85 °C under reduce pressure 600 mm Hg, recycle ionic liquids used in next synthesis compounds. All the synthesized compounds were subjected to various physico chemical measurement. The purity of the compounds were checked by TLC using silica gel-G as adsorbent, UV light or iodine to accomplish visualization. The molecular weights were determined by the Rast Camphor method¹⁸. Carbon and hydrogen analyses of the compounds were performed at the Microanalytical Laboratory of the Department of Chemistry, Punjab University, Chandigarh. Sulfur and nitrogen were determined by Messenger's¹⁹ and Kjeldahl's methods²⁰ respectively. IR spectra were recorded on a Nicolet Megna FTIR-550 spectrophotometer using KBr pellets. The ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectra were obtained on a Bruker DRX-300 NMR spectrometer at 300 MHz and 75 MHz respectively in DMSO-*d*₆ using TMS as the internal standard. Mass spectrum of representative compound was recorded on Kratos 50 mass spectrometer at 70 eV. All the melting points were determined using the open-ended capillary tube method and are uncorrected. The structures and reaction scheme of compounds are shown in Figs. 1 and 2.

Fig. 1. Preparation of ionic liquid [BMIM][TFA].

Fig. 2. Preparation of thiazolidinone derivative using 2-mercaptoacetic acid.

Results and discussion

The physical properties and analytical data of the thiazolidinone derivative, synthesized in acidic ionic liquid are enlisted in Table 1. As indicated in the Table 1, we have observed that the yield of compounds which contain electron withdrawing group is more than compounds having electron donating group. The time utilized for the synthesis of compounds using ionic liquid as a media is less as compared to commercial hazardous solvents. It is also observed that the isolation of prepared compounds is more easy and eco-friendly in ionic liquid as compared to other hazardous solvents. All the synthesized compounds are stable at ambient temperature, slightly soluble in ethanol, methanol and very soluble in DMF and DMSO.

Spectral data :

2-(4-Fluorophenyl)-5-methyl-3-(6-methylpyridin-2-yl)thiazolidin-4-one (4a) :

IR (KBr) ν_{\max} in cm^{-1} : 2966–2870 (C-H), 1714.79 (C=O), 1610 (C=N), 783 (C-F); ^1H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO; δ/ppm relative to TMS) : δ 7.00–7.08 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.03 (1H, d, Ar-H), 7.72 (1H, t, Ar-H), 7.63 (1H, d, Ar-H), 6.52 (1H, s, CH), 3.54 (1H, q, CH), 2.61 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.86 (3H, d, CH_3); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 173.43 (d, J 1059.0

Hz), 156.53 (s), 150.12 (s), 145.85 (s), 135.40 (s), 128.86–128.14 (m), 119.58 (s), 116.64 (s), 116.55–114.07 (m), 64.88 (s), 46.49 (s), 24.27 (s), 17.86 (s); MS : m/z 302.09.

2-(4-Chlorophenyl)-5-methyl-3-(6-methylpyridin-2-yl)thiazolidin-4-one (4b) :

IR (KBr) ν_{\max} in cm^{-1} : 2934–2840 (C-H), 1701 (C=O), 1595 (C=N), 826.87 (C-F); ^1H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO; δ/ppm relative to TMS) : δ 7.20–7.25 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.00 (1H, d, Ar-H), 7.77 (1H, t, Ar-H), 7.60 (1H, d, Ar-H), 6.55 (1H, s, CH), 3.58 (1H, q, CH), 2.68 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.89 (3H, d, CH_3); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 176.84 (s), 167.91 (s), 167.09 (s), 135.40 (s), 128.86–128.14 (m), 116.82–114.07 (m), 103.62 (s), 68.12 (s), 46.73 (s), 28.13 (s), 24.38 (s), 17.85 (s); MS : m/z 318.06.

2-(4-Bromophenyl)-5-methyl-3-(6-methylpyridin-2-yl)thiazolidin-4-one (4c) :

IR (KBr) ν_{\max} in cm^{-1} : 2907–2886 (C-H), 1702 (C=O), 1630 (C=N), 684.14 (C-F); ^1H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO; δ/ppm relative to TMS) : δ 7.15–7.45 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.03 (1H, d, Ar-H), 7.78 (1H, t, Ar-H), 7.69 (1H, d, Ar-H), 6.58 (1H, s, CH), 3.57 (1H, q, CH), 2.66 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.88 (3H, d, CH_3); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 177.77 (s), 157.53 (s),

Table 1. Analytical data and physical properties of compounds (4a-g)

Compds.	Melting point (°C)	R	Found (Calcd.) (%)				Mol. wt. Found (Calcd.)	Yield (%)
			C	H	N	S		
[BMIM][TFA] ($\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{15}\text{F}_3\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$)	–	–	47.28 (47.62)	6.03 (5.99)	11.64 (11.11)	–	266.54 (252.23)	95
4a ($\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{15}\text{FN}_2\text{OS}$)	172–175	F	64.73 (63.56)	5.97 (5.00)	10.12 (9.26)	11.23 (10.60)	306.08 (302.37)	92
4b ($\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{15}\text{ClN}_2\text{OS}$)	194–199	Cl	63.43 (60.28)	5.12 (4.74)	9.65 (8.79)	11.08 (10.06)	326.25 (318.82)	90
4c ($\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{15}\text{BrN}_2\text{OS}$)	223–229	Br	55.76 (52.90)	4.86 (4.16)	8.3 (7.71)	9.43 (8.83)	370.59 (363.27)	93
4d ($\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{15}\text{BrN}_2\text{OS}$)	185–188	CH_3	70.58 (68.42)	6.68 (6.08)	9.97 (9.39)	11.70 (10.75)	306.43 (298.40)	90
4e ($\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{OS}$)	160–165	H	71.38 (67.58)	6.00 (5.67)	10.35 (9.85)	12.04 (11.28)	292.72 (284.38)	92
4f ($\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{OS}$)	206–211	OCH_3	69.52 (64.94)	6.12 (5.77)	9.42 (8.91)	11.03 (10.20)	322.53 (314.40)	86
4g ($\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}$)	263–268	OH	67.88 (63.98)	5.90 (5.37)	10.81 (9.33)	11.94 (10.67)	307.64 (300.18)	84
($\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}$)								

150.12 (s), 145.85 (s), 138.37 (s), 132.75–132.36 (m), 129.29–128.89 (m), 121.18 (s), 119.58 (s), 116.64 (s), 64.88 (s), 46.49 (s), 24.27 (s), 17.85 (s); MS : m/z 362.01.

5-Methyl-3-(6-methylpyridin-2-yl)-2-p-tolylthiazolidin-4-one (4d) :

IR (KBr) ν_{\max} in cm^{-1} : 2944–2875 (C-H), 1694 (C=O), 1594 (C=N), 1410.52 (C-CH₃); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO; δ /ppm relative to TMS) : δ 7.15–7.22 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.00 (1H, d, Ar-H), 7.80 (1H, t, Ar-H), 7.81 (1H, d, Ar-H), 6.48 (1H, s, CH), 3.55 (1H, q, CH), 2.63 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.32 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.91 (3H, d, CH₃); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 177.77 (s), 157.53 (s), 150.12 (s), 145.85 (s), 139.08 (s), 137.07 (s), 130.17–129.96 (m), 126.56–126.34 (m), 119.58 (s), 116.64 (s), 64.88 (s), 46.49 (s), 24.27 (s), 21.13 (s), 17.85 (s); MS : m/z 298.11.

5-Methyl-3-(6-methylpyridin-2-yl)-2-phenylthiazolidin-4-one (4e) :

IR (KBr) ν_{\max} in cm^{-1} : 2974–2863 (C-H), 1685 (C=O), 1590 (C=N), 649 (C-CH₃); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO; δ /ppm relative to TMS) : δ 7.25–7.32 (5H, m, Ar-H), 7.00 (1H, d, Ar-H), 7.78 (1H, t, Ar-H), 7.83 (1H, d, Ar-H), 6.45 (1H, s, CH), 3.59 (1H, q, CH), 2.60 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.90 (3H, d, CH₃); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 177.77 (s), 157.53 (s), 150.12 (s), 145.85 (s), 139.63 (s), 129.20 (s), 129.01–128.85 (m), 127.39–126.99 (m), 119.58 (s), 116.64 (s), 64.88 (s), 46.49 (s), 24.27 (s), 17.85 (s); MS : m/z 284.10.

2-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-5-methyl-3-(6-methylpyridin-2-yl)thiazolidin-4-one (4f) :

IR (KBr) ν_{\max} in cm^{-1} : 2992–2889 (C-H), 1677 (C=O), 1584 (C=N), 987 (C-CH₃); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO; δ /ppm relative to TMS) : δ 6.98–7.20 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.06 (1H, d, Ar-H), 7.89 (1H, t, Ar-H), 7.80 (1H, d, Ar-H), 6.50 (1H, s, CH), 3.59 (1H, q, CH), 2.63 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.85 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.90 (3H, d, CH₃); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 177.77 (s), 160.89 (s), 157.53 (s), 150.12 (s), 145.85 (s), 133.80 (s), 127.30–127.08 (m), 119.58 (s), 116.64 (s), 114.37–114.15 (m), 64.88 (s), 56.04 (s), 46.49

(s), 24.27 (s), 17.85 (s); MS : m/z 314.11.

2-(4-Hydroxyphenyl)-5-methyl-3-(6-methylpyridin-2-yl)thiazolidin-4-one (4g) :

IR (KBr) ν_{\max} in cm^{-1} : 2956–2848 (C-H), 1688 (C=O), 1625 (C=N), 3614 (C-OH); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO; δ /ppm relative to TMS) : δ 7.50–7.72 (4H, m, Ar-H), 6.90 (1H, d, Ar-H), 7.70 (1H, t, Ar-H), 7.71 (1H, d, Ar-H), 6.54 (1H, s, CH), 3.57 (1H, q, CH), 2.62 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.72 (1H, s, O-H), 1.95 (3H, d, CH₃); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 177.77 (s), 159.71 (s), 157.53 (s), 150.12 (s), 145.85 (s), 131.37 (s), 128.56–128.35 (m), 119.58 (s), 116.64 (s), 116.27–116.06 (m), 64.88 (s), 46.49 (s), 24.27 (s), 17.85 (s); MS : m/z 300.09.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have developed a versatile, useful and environment benign method for the synthesis of thiazolidone using ionic liquid as a solvent. Present methodology was further extended to pyridine substituted thiazolidone. Synthesized compounds were fully characterized by IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR and Mass spectra. The present methodology developed herein in general and expands the application of ionic liquids for the synthesis of more diverse thiazolidone, which are of high importance in medicinal chemistry. Further studies of this synthetic protocol are under progress and will be reported in due course.

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